

Comparison on Sedative Effect of Dexmedetomidine and Propofol Infusion in Patients undergoing Middle Ear Surgeries in a Tertiary Care HospitalChandamita Bhagabati¹, Rupankar Nath², Deepannita Sutradhar³, Suneeta Dutta⁴¹Post Graduate Resident, Department of Anaesthesiology and Critical care, Silchar Medical College and Hospital, Assam²Associate professor, Department of Anaesthesiology and Critical care, Silchar Medical College and Hospital, Assam³Associate professor, Department of Anaesthesiology and Critical care, Silchar Medical College and Hospital, Assam⁴Professor and HOD, Department of Anaesthesiology and Critical care, Silchar Medical College and Hospital, Assam

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background and Aim:** Conscious sedation offers numerous advantages, including the promotion of stable hemodynamics and reduction of intraoperative bleeding [1]. The purpose of our study is to compare the efficiency of sedation between two infusions dexmedetomidine and propofol in patients having middle ear procedures with conscious sedation.**Methodology:** The research was performed at Silchar Medical College with consent from the Institutional Ethical Committee. It was constructed as a prospective randomized controlled experiment with a double-blinded methodology. Eighty patients having middle ear procedures ranging in age from 18 to 60, were split into two groups at random. Group P received an infusion of propofol commencing with a loading dosage of 75 mcg/kg over 10 minutes followed by a sustained dose of 50 mcg/kg/hr, whereas Group D received an infusion of dexmedetomidine with a loading dose of 1 mcg/kg over 10 minutes and a sustained dose of 0.4 mcg/kg/hr. Hemodynamic parameters and patients' requirement for rescue analgesia were documented. Any adverse events, including bradycardia, hypotension and respiratory depression, were promptly identified and managed according to established protocol.**Result:** In our study, we noted that Group P achieved adequate sedation more quickly (11±1.5 min) than Group D (16.4±1.7 min), with a p-value of <0.001 indicating significant difference between the two. Notably, Group D experienced a pronounced change in heart rate following the loading dose administration, whereas Group P showed a significant alteration in mean arterial pressure (MAP) after receiving its loading dose. Group P exhibited a higher need for rescue analgesia due to higher VAS score and lower IOWA patient satisfaction score.**Conclusion:** Our study suggested that dexmedetomidine is a superior sedative agent compared to propofol for middle ear surgeries, as it maintains relatively stable hemodynamics and requires less rescue analgesia, resulting in an improved IOWA score.**Keywords:** Conscious Sedation, Dexmedetomidine Infusion, Propofol Infusion.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Conscious sedation is described as "a controlled, pharmacologically induced, minimally depressed level of consciousness that allows the patient to maintain a patent airway independently and continuously, with the ability to respond appropriately to physical stimulation and/or verbal commands" [2]. Drugs that can be used to induce conscious sedation include propofol, alpha 2 receptor agonist and benzodiazepines. This approach offers several advantages, including reduced induction time and relative hemodynamic

stability. Currently, this technique is being employed in middle ear surgeries. Typical middle ear procedures such as cortical or modified radical mastoidectomies, myringotomies, tympanoplasties, grommet insertion, and cochlear implantation may be conducted using either general anaesthesia or local anaesthesia. During middle ear surgeries, specific aspects to address include maintaining a clear surgical site without bleeding, carefully positioning the patient's head, managing the airway, monitoring facial nerves, understanding the

impact of nitrous oxide during middle ear procedures, promoting a comfortable recovery, and preventing postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV). While most middle ear surgeries are conducted under general anaesthesia for patient comfort and surgeon ease, local anaesthesia is a cost-effective alternative that typically results in shorter operative times. However, patients undergoing surgery under local anaesthesia may experience discomforts such as noise sensations, anxiety, dizziness, backaches, claustrophobia, or earaches. Therefore, combining conscious sedation with local anaesthesia is preferred, as it may alleviate these adverse effects [3]. In this study, we investigated middle ear surgeries performed under conscious sedation using two drugs: dexmedetomidine and propofol.

Dexmedetomidine is a sedative and analgesic drug that acts centrally on alpha 2 receptors, known for producing these effects without putting the patient into respiratory distress. Additionally, it functions as a sympatholytic agent, capable of mitigating the stress response to surgery, thus promoting hemodynamic stability. Studies have indicated considerable decrease in the amount of opioids needed during and following surgery [4].

Propofol is a sedative-hypnotic agent commonly used for induction of general anaesthesia as well as for procedural sedation during monitored anaesthesia. Propofol is widely recognized as the preferred choice for intraoperative sedation in day care surgeries because of its quick onset and faster recovery time and ease of adjustment in dosage. Propofol reduces ventilatory drive in a dose-dependent manner by inhibiting the response to elevated carbon dioxide levels. This suppression of respiratory function is exacerbated when propofol is administered alongside other sedative medications like opioids, benzodiazepines, or centrally acting alpha 2 agonists [5].

This research seeks to evaluate the sedative and hypnotic effects of dexmedetomidine and propofol. By the study's conclusion, we anticipate to determine the superior drug for sedating patients undergoing middle ear surgeries with local anaesthesia. We aim for the findings of this investigation to offer valuable guidance to anaesthesiologists in choosing the most appropriate drug for routine clinical practice.

Methods and Materials

This double-blind randomized controlled experiment was carried out at Silchar Medical College and Hospital over the course of a year, from March 2023 to February 2024, after receiving clearance from the Institutional Ethics Committee and being registered with the Clinical Trials Registry (CTRI/2023/07/055887).

We included patients aged 18-60 years that were ASA Grades 1 and 2 undergoing elective middle ear surgeries. Patients who had allergic reactions to the study drugs, pregnant patients, patients suffering with persistent upper respiratory infections respiratory dysfunction and obese patients were not included in the study.

Eighty patients were recruited for the research and divided into two groups at random, with each group comprising forty patients.

Group D: Patients received an infusion of dexmedetomidine with a loading dose of 1 mcg/kg over 10 minutes and a sustained dose of 0.4 mcg/kg/hr.

Group P: Patients receiving an infusion of propofol commencing with a loading dosage of 75 mcg/kg over 10 minutes followed by a sustained dose of 50 mcg/kg/hr.

Electrocardiogram, SPO2 and non-invasive blood pressure monitoring were used as part of routine monitoring. All patients received 6 L/min of oxygen through face masks throughout the surgery. Injections of fentanyl (1 mcg/kg), glycopyrrolate (0.2 mg), and ondansetron (4 mg) were administered as premedication to the patients.

Following premedication, the corresponding loading doses and infusions of either propofol or dexmedetomidine were started according to the designated group. Before performing surgery on patients who had a Ramsay score of 3, surgeons were directed to paint, drape, and locally infiltrate the operating site with 2% lidocaine and 1/100,000 epinephrine. Patients' hemodynamic parameters were recorded with observations made at 5-minute intervals throughout the first 20 minutes of the procedure and then every 10 minutes until the procedure was finished.

Patients were evaluated for pain or any movement during infiltration of local anesthesia. A 10-point verbal scale was used to record pain, with 0 denoting no discomfort and 10 denoting maximum discomfort. Inj Fentanyl 1 µg/kg rescue bolus was administered to those individuals who responded with a visual analogue pain score greater than 4 or who demonstrated movement during infiltration.

The study drug infusion rate was adjusted during intra operative period to maintain adequate level of sedation (RSS 3) and respiration rate of >12 breaths/min and SpO2 >94% indicating normal respiratory and cardiovascular function. If the respiration rate was less than 12 bpm or the SpO2 was less than 94%, the sedation was terminated. Patients who needed higher loading dosage than what was prescribed in order to get a sufficient level of sedation were not included in the trial.

Adverse effects like hypotension (MAP<65mmHg), Bradycardia (HR<60 mmHg) hypoventilation (RR<12/min), vomiting, nausea and dry mouth were evaluated, recorded, and managed with intravenous fluids and medications as necessary.

Statistical Analysis: Based on previous literature (4), it was assumed that to observe a minimum 9.5 point difference between two groups a total of 40 samples will be required per group to detect 80% power at 5% level of significance.

$$\frac{2\sigma^2(Z_{\beta} + Z_{\alpha/2})^2}{d^2}$$

All collected data were inputted into MS Excel 2010 and analyzed using SPSS version 21 to assess statistical significance. Fisher's exact test and chi-square were used to look at the association between categorical variables. The normality of the data was assessed using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests. An independent t-test was utilized to compare the mean difference between two groups, taking into account whether the

normality assumption for continuous variables was satisfied. The Mann-Whitney test was employed for non-normally distributed data. Descriptive statistics were presented by using tables and bar diagram.

At 5% level of significance, Statistical significance between the groups was interpreted as follows:

- p value > 0.05 = not significant
- p value < 0.05= significant

Results and Observation:

Demographic variables such as age, sex, height, weight, mean duration of surgery, and ASA physical status were similar between both groups and did not exhibit statistically significant differences (p > 0.05).

Time to achieve Ramsay sedation score 3 was noted in both groups, Group P (11±1.5 min) and Group D (16.4±1.7 min). The observed difference between them was found to be highly statistically significant with a p-value <0.001. [Table:1] However, Ramsay sedation score was comparable in both groups. P-value is calculated by using Mann Whitney test.

Table 1: Mean Ramsay Sedation Score in both groups:

	Group D	Group P	p value
Time to achieve RSS3	16.4±1.7	11±1.5	<0.001
RSS 30 MIN	3±0	3±0	1.000
RSS 40 MIN	2.95±0.22	2.83±0.38	0.079
RSS 50 MIN	2.83±0.38	2.7±0.46	0.192
RSS 60 MIN	2.78±0.42	2.75±0.44	0.794
RSS 70 MIN	2.9±0.3	2.85±0.36	0.502
RSS 80 MIN	2.88±0.33	2.75±0.44	0.155
RSS 90 MIN	2.8±0.41	2.7±0.46	0.305
RSS 100 MIN	2.85±0.36	2.75±0.44	0.267
RSS 110 MIN	2.83±0.38	2.95±0.22	0.079
RSS 120 MIN	2.97±0.17	2.87±0.34	0.112
RSS 130 MIN	2.75±0.44	2.73±0.45	0.842
RSS 140 MIN	2.71±0.47	2.5±0.51	0.193
RSS 150 MIN	2.5±0.55	2.38±0.52	0.652
RSS 160 MIN	2.5±0.58	2.4±0.55	0.777
RSS 170 MIN	2.5±0.71	2±0	0.317
RSS 180 MIN	2.5±0.71	3±0	0.317

Figure 1:

In group D, change in Heart Rate was significant (p -value <0.001) after administration of loading dose of dexmedetomidine in the first 15 minutes and also in cases where duration of surgery exceeds 90 minutes. In Group P, such variability is not seen. (Table 2) Unpaired t-test is used to calculate p value

Table 2: Heart rate variation at various time intervals in both the group

Time	Group D	Group P	p value
HR 0	83.6 \pm 12.5	88.5 \pm 13.9	0.107
HR 5 MIN	74.2 \pm 8.5	84.8 \pm 9.5	<0.001
HR 10 MIN	68.4 \pm 6.7	81.4 \pm 7.1	<0.001
HR 15 MIN	66.2 \pm 4.3	75.2 \pm 9.6	<0.001
HR 20 MIN	66.3 \pm 5.3	69.1 \pm 7.1	0.053
HR 30 MIN	67.7 \pm 5	70.4 \pm 7.2	0.056
HR 40 MIN	68.4 \pm 4.2	70.1 \pm 5.3	0.113
HR 50 MIN	66 \pm 4.4	68.1 \pm 7.0	0.105
HR 60 MIN	65.2 \pm 4.3	68.8 \pm 10.8	0.056
HR 70 MIN	64.7 \pm 4.8	68 \pm 9.2	0.052
HR 80 MIN	67.1 \pm 5.5	69.2 \pm 6.1	0.117
HR 90 MIN	64.9 \pm 4.1	68.8 \pm 9.5	0.019
HR 100 MIN	65.1 \pm 4.2	78.3 \pm 13	<0.001
HR 110 MIN	66 \pm 3.9	74.2 \pm 11	<0.001
HR 120 MIN	66.4 \pm 4.6	72.5 \pm 10.5	0.002
HR 130 MIN	66.8 \pm 3.8	73.7 \pm 10.8	0.002
HR 140 MIN	63.8 \pm 2.5	73.2 \pm 9.6	<0.001
HR 150 MIN	63 \pm 4.2	76.6 \pm 8.4	0.004
HR 160 MIN	59.5 \pm 2.4	70 \pm 4.5	0.004
HR 170 MIN	59.5 \pm 0.7	71 \pm 3.6	0.024
HR 180 MIN	56.5 \pm 0.7	70 \pm 1.4	0.007

Figure 2:

Regarding variation in MAP, our study demonstrated that in Group P, change in Mean Arterial Pressure was significant (p value <0.001) after administration of loading dose of propofol in

the first 20 minutes. However, Group D did not show any significant alteration in MAP following administration of its loading dose. Unpaired t-test was used to determine the p value.

Table 3: Table showing variation in MAP at various time intervals

	Group D	Group P	p value
MAP 0 MIN	88.7±6.2	85.8±7	0.053
MAP 5 MIN	87.1±4.2	74.8±2.7	<0.001
MAP 10 MIN	85.7±5.2	70.6±4.1	<0.001
MAP 15 MIN	87.8±7.2	68.1±4.1	<0.001
MAP 20 MIN	91.1±8.8	71±4.3	<0.001
MAP 30 MIN	85±11.8	81.1±5.4	0.06
MAP 40 MIN	86.7±6.6	84±6.5	0.061
MAP 50 MIN	92.9±7.6	90.5±6	0.129
MAP 60 MIN	93.6±9	89.9±7.6	0.053
MAP 70 MIN	91.4±8	89.1±4.8	0.11
MAP 80 MIN	85.3±6.5	83±3.9	0.054
MAP 90 MIN	86.3±11	82.7±4.6	0.059
MAP 100 MIN	86.9±9.3	84.3±6.6	0.155
MAP 110 MIN	88.9±8	86.7±4	0.115
MAP 120 MIN	93.2±9.7	89.4±6.9	0.051
MAP 130 MIN	87.8±9.8	84.4±7.9	0.139
MAP 140 MIN	87±9.9	83±7.6	0.148
MAP 150 MIN	75±9.7	74.1±6.4	0.842
MAP 160 MIN	71±8	70.6±1.1	0.913
MAP 170 MIN	73.5±16.3	71±2	0.793
MAP 180 MIN	75.5±17.7	74±1.4	0.916

Figure 3:

In our study, parameters such as Respiratory Rate, Oxygen Saturation, and Ramsay sedation score were similar between both groups and did not show statistically significant differences. In terms of rescue analgesia requirement, group P needed a

mean rescue analgesia of 65.38 mcg whereas group D needed 21 mcg which indicates that Group P needed a greater amount of analgesics compared to Group D. P value (<0.001) was calculated using Mann-Whitney test.

Figure 4: Figure showing mean rescue analgesia in both groups

In our study, mean Visual Analogue Pain score in group D was 3.58 whereas in group P it was 6.40. Thus higher VAS score in Group P compared to Group D, reflects the greater need for rescue analgesia in Group P. Mann-Whitney test was used to calculate the p value which showed high statistical significance.

Figure 5: Figure showing VAS score in both groups

In our study, mean IOWA Patient Satisfaction score in group D was 0.6105 and in group P it was 0.3480 which indicates that patients have higher satisfaction with dexmedetomidine compared to propofol. The p-value was determined using the Mann-Whitney test.

Figure 6: Mean IOWA patient satisfaction score in both groups

The Surgeon Satisfaction Score in dexmedetomidine group was 5.1 whereas in propofol group it was 2.97. This indicates higher Surgeon satisfaction score in group D compared to group P. Mann-Whitney test was used to calculate p value.

Figure 7: Figure showing Surgeon Satisfaction score in both groups

In our study, adverse effects like Bradycardia was observed in 7 (17.5%) patients in Group D.

Chi square test was used to determine the p value (<0.001)

Our study showed that hypotension was present in 3 (7.5%) patients in Group D and 6 (15%) patients

in Group P. p-value (0.288) was calculated using chi square test.

Nausea was observed in 2 (5%) patients in Group D, whereas vomiting, hypoventilation were not observed in any group. p-value (2) was calculated using chi square test.

Discussion

A research by Godbole et al. [6] concluded that dexmedetomidine and propofol are both useful for inducing hypotensive anaesthesia during ENT surgeries. However, compared to propofol, dexmedetomidine is more efficient in preserving hemodynamic stability, a finding that aligns with our study.

In our study, it was observed that propofol induced adequate sedation more quickly (11 ± 1.5 min) than dexmedetomidine (16.4 ± 1.7 min), with a p-value indicating high statistical significance (<0.001). The results of our experiment are consistent with the results reported by Nasreen F et al. [18]. However, our findings contrast with the findings of Liu Weihua et al. [7] study. Their study reported that there was no significant differences between these two drugs in terms of induction time and recovery time. Our study demonstrated that 7 (17.5%) patients developed bradycardia in the dexmedetomidine group. Ayuglu H et al [19] also reported bradycardia as an adverse effect of dexmedetomidine infusion in their study which was treated with anticholinergic drugs. In our investigation, during the first 15 minutes of the loading dosage of dexmedetomidine administration, there was a noticeable and statistically significant alteration in heart rate which was more pronounced in cases where the duration of surgery exceeded 90 minutes. This observation is consistent with findings from the research carried out by Alhashemi et al. [15], which also reported higher occurrences of bradycardia in dexmedetomidine group.

Our investigation revealed a noticeable and statistically significant alteration in Mean Arterial Pressure within the first 20 minutes after the loading dosage of propofol was administered. Three (7.5%) patients receiving an infusion of dexmedetomidine and six (15%) patients receiving an infusion of propofol had hypotension. Similar results were seen in a research by Wu Y et al [16], where the propofol group experienced a substantial drop in MAP from baseline during the surgery. These outcomes were consistent with the research of Verma et al. [1], which showed that propofol usage is linked to a higher risk of hemodynamic instability (hypotension). On the other hand, a research by Ghali Ashraf et al. showed that individuals taking propofol and dexmedetomidine had a comparable substantial decrease in MAP (8).

Our study, supported by studies of Nallam et al. [3], demonstrated a higher requirement for rescue analgesia with propofol compared to dexmedetomidine. Similarly, Vega et al. [12] found dexmedetomidine to be superior for monitored anaesthesia care, providing improved intraoperative analgesia even with lower maintenance doses. However, a research by Karanth et al. revealed that patients receiving propofol infusion and those

receiving dexmedetomidine had comparable needs for rescue analgesia [9].

According to our study, higher VAS scores were observed in propofol group in comparison to dexmedetomidine group which was consistent with Gandhi et al.'s findings [13]. Iowa patient satisfaction scores were greater for patients in dexmedetomidine group, similar to the findings of Kumar M. Chandra et al. [10].

Surgeon satisfaction scores were also noted to be superior in dexmedetomidine group, aligning with Verma et al.'s findings [1], which were further supported by the results of the study conducted by Arain and Ebert [11]. According to a research by Kim et al., propofol causes respiratory distress more frequently than dexmedetomidine (11%).

Dexmedetomidine sedation was shown to be safe in another trial by Taghinia et al. [17] since it did not result in drop in oxygen saturation and also lessened the requirement for the administration of additional medications. In contrast, our study found no instances of respiratory depression in either group under monitored anaesthesia care.

In our study, we observed that 2 patients (5%) reported nausea after prolonged dexmedetomidine infusion (duration >150 mins), none of the participants in the propofol group reported nausea or vomiting during the study. This finding contrasts with the results reported by Virkkila M, where neither group experienced any incidence of nausea and vomiting (20)

Conclusion

Our study revealed dexmedetomidine as a superior sedative agent to propofol for middle ear procedures conducted under monitored anaesthesia care. Dexmedetomidine infusion exhibited stable hemodynamics and reduced the need for rescue analgesia, along with lower VAS scores and improved IOWA score.

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